

Salicyloyl hydrazide as a Reagent for Industrial Analysis: Estimation of Titanium

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A method for the estimation of titanium in industrial samples like bauxite, ilmenite, titaniferrous magnetite, ferrotitanium etc., with salicyloyl hydrazide has been described. The reagent precipitates Ti effectively and quantitatively in the pH range 3.5-4.5, iron being masked with EDTA.

Salicyloyl hydrazide was first prepared by Strauve and Radenhausen¹. It was used by Shome and coworkers² as a reagent for gravimetric estimation of Pd. In the present communication, a method for the estimation of titanium in industrial analysis of ores and alloys like bauxite, ilmenite, titaniferrous magnetite, ferrotitanium etc., with this reagent is described. The precipitation of Ti with salicyloyl hydrazide in the pH range 3.5-4.5 is quantitative. With the aid of EDTA as a masking agent, the interference of metals generally associated with the above samples can be overcome easily and effectively.

The method is comparatively simple and efficient and the results obtained are comparable to those obtained by long standard procedures.

Titanium when present in considerable amounts along with reasonable amounts of iron and aluminium in complex materials like ores and alloys offers many difficulties in its estimation by the conventional methods. The usual procedure³ for its estimation in these materials consists in removing iron first in tartarate medium by ammoniacal H₂S and then precipitating titanium from ice cold solution (2NH₂SO₄) with cupferron and then igniting the precipitate to TiO₂. Much difficulty is experienced in this procedure and sometimes repetition of the process of separation of iron becomes essential when both iron and titanium are present in comparable amounts. Besides, the precipitate of titanium-cupferronate needs controlled ignition and the whole process thus becomes tedious and time consuming. Other methods⁴ for the determination of titanium in ores, alloys and minerals are the colorimetric method based on the use of H₂O₂, and volumetric method based on the reduction of titanium by zinc and titrating with ferric alum in the presence of potassium thiocyanate as indicator. The former method is limited in application in solutions containing not more than 0.1 mg/ml. The volumetric method is less dependable and subject to error, unless special care is taken to prevent reoxidation of the reduced titanium during the operation.

1. Strauve and Radenhausen, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1930, **52**, 239.
2. H. R. Das and S. C. Shome, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1965, **32**, 400.
3. G. F. Lundell, H. A. Bright and J. I. Hofman. *Applied Inorganic Analysis*. (Interscience Publishers Inc., New York), 1955, 580.
4. F. C. Piggott. *Ferrous Analysis*. (Chapman and Hall, London), 1953, 485.

It has been observed during the present investigation that the precipitation of titanium with salicyloyl hydrazide is complete in the pH range 3.5–4.5 even in the presence of EDTA. Although EDTA was advantageously used for masking large quantity of iron, it is important to adjust the amount of EDTA in this estimation and a slight excess is recommended. The disappearance of violet colour of the iron-complex serves as an indication of the slight excess of EDTA.

The precipitate of the titanium compound is granular and can be filtered as such through a sintered glass crucible (No. 3 or 4), the composition of the precipitate after drying at 120° for 1 hr, is given by $TiOR_2$ when R is a molecule of salicyloyl hydrazide minus a hydrogen atom.

Above pH 5.0 a slight contamination of the titanium precipitate with iron has been noticed and this cannot be avoided. The precipitation is, therefore, recommended to be carried out in the pH range 3.5–4.5.

TABLE

Estimation of titanium in some ores and alloys by the standard and salicyloyl hydrazide methods.

Material	Major constituents	TiO ₂	
		Standard method	Salicyloyl hydrazide method
1) Ilmenite	7.05% FeO	51.89	51.80
	34.60% FeO	50.08	50.16
	31.08% FeO	49.98	49.90
2) Titaniferrous magnetite	68.51% Fe (total)	12.53	12.61
	56.13% Fe (total)	11.90	11.99
	57.53% Fe (total)	13.15	13.21
3) Bauxite	10.00% F ₂ O ₃ ⁺		
	50.15% Al ₂ O ₃	6.45	6.66
	10.01% Fe ₂ O ₃ ⁺		
	51.38% Al ₂ O ₃	9.32	9.50
	8.42% Fe ₂ O ₃ ⁺		
	52.10% Al ₂ O ₃	7.98	8.10
4) Ferrotitanium	56.32% Fe	40.53	40.68

Estimation of titanium in ores (ilmenite, titaniferrous magnetite or bauxite): The ore sample (0.05 g for 25% or more TiO₂ content) was fused with potassium bisulphate in a silica crucible. The fused mass was cooled and extracted with hot 2N H₂SO₄, filtered and the residue was washed with hot 1% H₂SO₄ solution. The combined filtrate and the washings

were neutralised with dilute ammonia till the appearance of an opalescence which was then dissolved in a minimum quantity of H_2SO_4 (3N). 1 ml of the reagent (1% in alcohol) was then added to the mixture followed by the addition of EDTA solution (0.4%) with stirring till the violet colour changed to lemon yellow. 1 ml more of EDTA solution was added. The mixture was warmed for a while and then was added a sufficient quantity of the reagent and kept on the water bath for about an hour when the precipitate coagulated. It was cooled to room temperature and filtered through weighed gooch (No. 3 or 4), washed with hot water and dried at 120° to a constant weight. From the difference in the weights the percentage of TiO_2 was calculated using the ratio $\text{TiO}_2/\text{TiO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2 = 0.2186$.

Estimation of titanium in alloys (Ferrotitanium): The alloy sample (0.05 gm) was dissolved in a mixture of 5–10 ml of concentrated HNO_3 and 5 ml concentrated HCl . About 5–10 ml of diluted (1 : 1) H_2SO_4 were added to it and the solution was slowly evaporated to fumes. It was then cooled to room temperature and water (25 ml) added cautiously. The solution was boiled to dissolve the solid mass completely. Silica was filtered off and the residue was washed thoroughly with hot water containing a little H_2SO_4 . Titanium was then estimated in the filtrate following the procedure described above. The results are recorded in the table.